

ESTIMATION OF LOCAL PERMEABILITY WITH ARTIFICIAL VISION TECHNIQUES USING A DIRECT METHOD

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1. Introduction

Measurement and characterization of fiber preform permeability is one of the main issues in composites process, since it plays a key role in process design and control. In fact, simulation is the only tool that allows guaranteeing a correct design and the success of the process, and the permeability is one critical input parameter needed by simulation. That's the reason why in industry, it is needed that the simulation and the reality are as close as possible, and so, the permeability must be as precise as possible.

However, in practice, permeability measurement is not a trivial task. In the literature of fibrous media permeability [5][6][7][8], large variations in permeability values have been reported even in well-controlled 1D or 2D flow experiments. It is found that the permeability can vary largely from case to case because of variations in preform microstructures and handling conditions, both of which may come from non-uniform raw material quality, improper preform preparation/loading, and mold assembling.

Moreover, the variation of the permeability can be caused not only in different process with similar conditions, but also in the same process. That means, the permeability may not be constant in every place of the preform.

In [1], a promising technique to measure permeability is proposed, called the inverse method. This is based on mixed numerical/ experimental technique (MNET), with the aim of matching the empirical data with the simulation. For that propose, the method iterates the value of permeability in the simulation until it matches the evolution of the experimentally measured flow front.

On the other hand, in our previous works [2][3][4], the Artificial Vision (AV) has been used as a tool to monitor LCM process, since by means a digital

camera it is possible to define the pixels as nodes and associate them as Finite Elements. This fact allows one using all the FE tools with the mesh defined by the camera. With this, mixed numerical/ experimental technique (MNET) is proposed to the computation of the discretized space observed by the camera as FE domain using a fixed mesh. With the camera, it is possible to measure the arrival time at which the flow achieves each node. Moreover, it is possible to measure the updating of the volume fraction of each element and also the flow front velocity since an amount of pixels can be associated with each mesh. It permits to calculate the percentage at which the mesh is filled. The pressure of each node cannot be measured but can be computed, given our possibilities to develop our MNET. As the measurements are "directly" the expected results of the simulation the proposed method is called "direct method".

2. Mixed numerical/experimental technique (MNET) by the use of direct measurements.

Fig. 1 Schematics of the direct method.

For one hand, the pressure in each node only can be obtained by FEM simulation. For the other hand it is possible to select the measured variables to work, as well as the type of mesh, fixed mesh, moving mesh, etc. If the updating of the volume fraction of each element is used to compute the material properties, the goal of this equations is to obtain the velocity to compute the material properties by the Darcy's law. The same occurs by the arrival time. For this reasons, the velocity computed by the camera is used in our proposed method. Then, our MNET works as follows: for one hand, computed velocity by the camera and the pressure obtained by the FEM simulation is combined in the darcy's law to obtain the material properties, see Fig.1

2.1 Meshing

For all the mesh possibilities that camera vision allows, fixed mesh, moving mesh, etc, we choose a meshing procedure by means of the concatenation of triangularly meshed gaps defined by consecutive flow fronts, so that all the nodes belong to some flow front Fig. 2

Fig. 2 Meshing Procedure

That configuration allows guarantee that there are no partially filled elements and so, the nodes' pressures can be computed with higher accuracy.

Moreover, with those characteristics, gradient pressure is always perpendicular to the flow front so that, the velocity vector and gradient pressures are collinear.

2.2 Obtaining Velocity by means Artificial Vision

Computation of velocities at flow front can be estimated by means the distance and time between consecutive flow fronts. To compute pixels' velocities a numerical approximation of velocity is applied, concretely the forward(1), backward(2) and central(3) difference method in the initial, final and intermediate flow fronts respectively.

$$\vec{V}_K \cong \frac{\vec{r}_{K+1} - \vec{r}_K}{t_{K+1} - t_K} \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{V}_K \cong \frac{\vec{r}_K - \vec{r}_{K-1}}{t_K - t_{K-1}} \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{V}_K \cong \frac{\vec{r}_{K+1} - \vec{r}_{K-1}}{t_{K+1} - t_{K-1}} \quad (3)$$

Where \vec{r}_K is the position of the pixel in the current flow front, \vec{r}_{K+1} is the position of the closest pixel in the next flow front and \vec{r}_{K-1} is the position of the closest pixel in the previous flow front.

For the computation of the velocities of each FE, the arithmetic mean of the velocities of the flow front pixels which belong to each FE

Fig. 3 Pixels' Velocities in the 5th flow front.

2.3 FEM Numerical Velocity Computation

A previous work [9] shown how can be solved the numerical simulation of RTM mould filling. This method is used here in order to compute the pressure gradient in the fixed triangular mesh generated through the artificial vision discretization.

Darcy's law can model the resin flow through a porous medium:

$$\vec{V} = -\frac{\underline{K}}{\phi \cdot \mu} \nabla P \quad (4)$$

where \vec{V} is the velocity vector, ϕ is the porosity, μ is the viscosity, P is the pressure and \underline{K} is a permeability tensor.

The fluid flow problem is defined in a volume Ω ,

$$\Omega = \Omega_f(t) \cup \Omega_e(t) \quad (5)$$

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where the fluid at time t occupies the volume $\Omega_f(t)$ and $\Omega_e(t)$ defines at that time the empty part of the mold. Assuming fluid incompressibility, the variational formulation related to the Darcy flow results

$$\int_{\Omega_f(t)} \left(\nabla p^* \cdot \frac{\underline{K}}{\phi \cdot \mu} \nabla p \right) d\Omega = 0 \quad (6)$$

where p^* denotes the usual weighting function. The prescribed conditions to impose on the boundary of $\Omega_f(t)$ are:

- The pressure gradient in the normal direction to the mold walls is zero.
- The pressure or the flow rate is specified at the injection nozzle.
- Zero pressure is applied on the flow front.

The flow kinematics can be computed by means of a conforming finite element Galerkin technique applied to the variational formulation extended to the whole domain Ω

The location of the fluid into the whole domain Ω is defined by the characteristic function I defined by

$$I(\underline{x}, t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \underline{x} \in \Omega_f(t) \\ 0 & \underline{x} \notin \Omega_f(t) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The evolution of the volume fraction, I , is given by the general linear advection equation:

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \frac{\partial I}{\partial t} + \underline{v} \cdot \nabla I = 0 \quad (8)$$

with $I=1$ on the inflow boundary.

So that, the resolution scheme is based in solving the three steps:

1. Obtain the pressure field using a finite elements discretization of the variational formulation given by Eq. (6) and imposing null pressure in the nodes contained by an empty element (i.e nodes 4, 5 and 6 in **Fig. 4**).
2. Compute the pressure gradient and the velocity field from Darcy's law
3. Update the element volume fraction, I , integrating the equation (8)

In our proposal, the meshing algorithm is developed in order to include all the control volumes that are completely filled, so that $I=1$. That information is obtained directly from the artificial vision as stated before. So in the method proposed, the updating of the volume fraction is not calculated with Eq.(8). This equation, and hence step 3, is only used in terms on the numerical evaluation of the proposed method.

Fig. 4 Fixed triangular mesh with control volumes in elements and computation of numerical flow velocities in elements

3. Estimation of Material Properties

In this section a methodology for estimating the local Material Properties based on Artificial Vision is described.

As has been shown in (4) Darcy's law describes the behavior of fluid in a porous medium.

However, if the porous medium is isotropic, tensor \underline{K} can be replaced by a number since $K_{xx} = K_{yy} = K$ so that, equation (4) can be expressed as (9),

$$\|V\| = M \cdot \|\nabla P\| \quad (9)$$

Where $M = \frac{K}{\phi \cdot \mu}$ represents the Material Properties

(MP), and the tensorial dimension has been removed since both vectors are collinear.

So that M can be computed as follows

$$M = \frac{\|V_{AV}\|}{\|\nabla P\|} \quad (10)$$

Where V_{AV} is the velocity obtained by means Artificial Vision, and ∇P is the gradient of pressure, obtained by means FEM simulation. However in order to compute FEM simulation the value of M is needed, and the equation results as follows

$$M^{est} = \frac{\|V_{AV}\|}{\|\nabla P(M^{est})\|} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) is a fixed-point equation whose solution is the real MP, since it matches the analytical model and the empirical measures. It can be proved that if the sequence defined in (12) converges, its limit value is a solution of equation (11)

$$M_{K+1}^{est} = \frac{\|V_{AV}\|}{\|\nabla P(M_K^{est})\|} \quad (12)$$

Our proposal consists in meshing the filled zone as explained in 2.1, and then, applying the sequence (12) until its convergence value, in the finite elements that belong to the gap defined between current flow front and the previous flow front. Velocity in each FE is computed as explained in 2.2, and the value obtained for M is maintained unchanged for the computations of posterior gaps.

3.1 Analysis for 1D model

In this section a demonstration of the convergence of sequence (12) in 1D model is provided taking the next assumptions:

- Artificial Vision provides the exact value of velocity \vec{V}_{AV} .
- All the MP of each finite element are known but the last one, that means the flow front.

From now on $H_w(M_i)$ denotes the Weighted Harmonic Mean (WHM) of M_i with weights L_i , varying i from 1 to N . Where M_i and L_i are the MP and the length of each 1D-Finite Element.

It can be proved that analytical Velocity for 1D model is (13) and analytical Gradient is (14)

$$V_{AV} = \frac{P_0}{X} H_w(M_i) \quad (13)$$

$$\nabla P(M_K^{est}) = \frac{P_0}{M_K^{est} X} H_w(M_1, \dots, M_{n-1}, M_K^{est}) \quad (14)$$

Where $X = \sum_1^n L_i$, i.e. the flow front position, and

P_0 is the injection pressure. So that,

$$M_{K+1}^{est} = \frac{\frac{P_0}{X} H_w(M_1, M_2, \dots, M_{n-1}, M_n)}{\frac{1}{M_K^{est}} \frac{P_0}{X} H_w(M_1, M_2, \dots, M_{n-1}, M_K^{est})} \quad (15)$$

Therefore, simplifying and applying the definition of WHM

$$M_{K+1}^{est} = M_K^{est} \left(1 - \frac{L_n H_w(M_i)}{X \cdot M_n} \right) + \frac{L_n H_w(M_i)}{X} \quad (16)$$

At this point, the aim consists in proving the convergence of the sequence defined by (16), since its limit value solves equation (11). That analysis is developed by means the Z-Transform.

Applying the Z-Transform in (16),

$$Z(M_Z^{est} - M_0^{est}) = M_Z^{est} \left(1 - \frac{L_n H_w(M_i)}{X \cdot M_n} \right) + \frac{L_n H_w(M_i)}{X} \frac{Z}{Z-1} \quad (17)$$

Where M_0^{est} is the initial value of the sequence. Simplifying,

$$M_Z^{est} = \frac{\left(\frac{L_n H_w(M_i)}{X} + M_0^{est} (Z-1) \right) Z}{(Z-1) \left(Z - \left(1 - \frac{L_n H_w(M_i)}{X \cdot M_n} \right) \right)} \quad (18)$$

According to the Final Value Theorem (FVT)

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} M_K^{est} = \lim_{Z \rightarrow 1} \frac{Z-1}{Z} M_Z^{est} = M_n \quad (19)$$

Therefore, if the sequence converges, it does to the correct value M_n independently of its initial value M_0^{est} .

However, the FVT guarantees the convergence iff the sequence is stable. That condition can be proved verifying all the poles of M_Z^{est} are in the unit circle. So that, the region of convergence (ROC) is:

$$\left| 1 - \frac{L_n H_w(M_i)}{X \cdot M_n} \right| < 1 \quad (20)$$

Since all values $L_n, H_w(M_i), X, M_n$ are real and positive, the ROC is:

$$0 < \frac{L_n H_w(M_i)}{X \cdot M_n} \leq 1 \quad (21)$$

$$1 < \frac{L_n H_w(M_i)}{X \cdot M_n} < 2 \quad (22)$$

With over-damped convergence behavior in the region defined by (21) and under-damped convergence behavior in the region defined by (22). So that, if the length of the last element is enough low that the equations (21) or (22) are verified the convergence is guaranteed.

Once that element is computed, a new flow front is obtained by means AV, and the MP of all FE are known but last one, so the hypothesis are verified, and the process can be restarted in the new gap.

4. Results

The described proposal has been applied to both simulating and real filling mold.

4.1 Simulation Results

The simulating filling mold has been realized using 2 different performs with isotropic permeabilities $K_1 = 10 \cdot 10^{-3} m^2$ and $K_2 = 2 \cdot 10^{-3} m^2$ in the fast and slow zone respectively, with $1 Pa \cdot s$ in viscosity and 1 in porosity.

Fig. 5 Simulation Setup

Fig. 6 Results of estimation of MP by color level

4.2 Experimental Results

The real filling mold has been realized using a main perform with 2 zones with different and lesser permeabilities.

Fig. 7 Experimental Setup

Fig. 8 Results of estimation of MP by color level

5. Conclusions

A new technique for estimating the local Material Properties in isotropic perform has been proposed. That approach can be used to obtain the permeability under controlled conditions.

An analytical demonstration of the correct convergence of the method in 1D has been provided. Finally, two tests with empirical and simulated data have been shown. These tests show the ability of the algorithm to detect different material properties' zones.

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